

Why Understanding the Big Data We Use for Research Matters – a Global Analysis of Flickr

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Abstract. Understanding the basic characteristics of a dataset is essential for making informed decisions on its suitability for research and beyond. Even simple descriptives, such as how much data there are overall and who produce it, are not easily acquired for big and user-generated data. We describe the spatio-temporal distribution of 229 million georeferenced posts by 1.5 million users in 2010–2022 on the photo-sharing platform Flickr. The platform’s popularity has declined, and increasingly the content is produced by a small group of super-users. Flickr is primarily used in the Global North. Additionally, we found that the platform’s public API did not respond consistently to spatially bounded queries. We conclude by discussing the possible impacts of these biases and data acquisition issues.

Keywords. social media, user-generated content, spatial bias, Flickr

1. Introduction

Social media platforms and other sources of people’s interactions have been exploited as a source of research data for well over 15 years now. Data sources ought to be understood to draw well-grounded conclusions from them (Gerring, 2012). However, big and user-generated data often lack basic information, such as how much data there are overall and who produce it – knowledge that is needed to make informed decisions on whether a source of data is suitable for a specific research context (McGrady et al., 2023).

The photo sharing site Flickr (est. 2004) has been used extensively for research purposes, for example, by using georeferenced photos as a

Published in “Proceedings of the 19th International Conference on Location Based Services (LBS 2025)”, edited by Juha Oksanen, Henrikki Tenkanen, Pyry Kettunen and Ville Mäkinen, LBS 2025 7-9 May 2025 Otaniemi, Espoo, Finland.

This contribution underwent double-blind peer review based on the paper. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15352535>
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proxy for people's nature visits (Tenkanen et al., 2017) and as a source of image content for training computer vision algorithms (Thomee et al., 2016). Flickr's research use is even disproportionately high compared to the platform's overall popularity (Toivonen et al., 2019) – yet, not much is known about the data. In this work, we analyzed Flickr's temporal (*when* question), spatial (*where*) and user base (*who*) characteristics globally, how these have changed as the platform has matured, and how reliable is the data acquisition process through the API. We aimed to identify the baggage and biases that can affect conclusions drawn from the data with this analysis.

2. Data and methods

We gathered all georeferenced photographs uploaded to Flickr using the Python tool *Flickrhistory* (Fink, 2022). We ran the collection twice and merged the unique posts from each run for a total of 229,033,020 entries by 1,517,834 users in 2010–2022. The home country of 431,073 users (26% of users) was then estimated based on self-reported information. We then aggregated use and users temporally by month and spatially to H3 global grid cells and country borders. To test data acquisition, we repeatedly queried a search endpoint with a spatially bounded query and recorded how many responses the API returned as a match.

3. Results

The most significant findings are presented in *Figure 1*. Flickr's popularity has consistently decreased over the 2010's in uploads and especially in the number of users uploading georeferenced photos (*Figure 1A* and *B*). The Pareto, or 80/20, principle is present in the data, as the most active 20% of users have uploaded 86% of the photos. Flickr's users and use (*Figure 1D* and *E*) are spatially concentrated in Europe, North America and Australia. Finally, Flickr's API does not respond consistently to repeated queries (mean 8910, std. 426) (*Figure 1F*).

Figure 1. Monthly counts of georeferenced photos (A) and active users (B) in thousands with seasonal LOESS trend lines. Share of photos uploaded by the most active 1, 10 and 20% in contrast to the other 80% of users (C). Distribution of Flickr users per country normalized by population (D). Weighted mean coordinate of Flickr’s use per photo-user-days (PUD) aggregated to H3 cells at level 4 in contrast to population distribution on the same grid (E). Number of photos returned by Flickr’s API for a bounding box covering the Teide National Park, Spain from 100 consecutive queries with a kernel density estimation fit over (F).

4. Conclusions

Irrespective of how Flickr data is used exactly, these findings are worth considering. The decline in popularity means using Flickr as a proxy for some phenomenon will show a declining time series regardless of how that phenomenon has actually developed. Even if change over time is not analysed,

the data will be increasingly older and not capture recent changes. The content is likely produced in the Global North by a small population of superusers. This may limit the contexts where Flickr is an accurate proxy for spatial and thematic phenomena. This is without considering other relevant demographics of the user base, such as age and gender. Finally, data acquisition from the platform introduces another source of uncertainty, which may affect reliability and reproducibility of research using it.

These issues are not unique to Flickr or social media data. In fact, it is the exceptional openness of Flickr that allows this analysis. The problem lies in that the most comprehensive, accurate, and timely sources of people's presence, mobilities, and activities are in datasets held by private companies. Research use of them is volatile, as data access can be closed at any time (Bruns, 2019) and the data accessed have unknown biases inherently, or introduced by black box preprocessing or APIs, as described above. One path forward could be public bodies offering transparently sourced and processed data products openly, such as the mobility dataset derived from mobile networking data in Spain (Ministerio de Transportes y Movilidad Sostenible, n.d.). Nonetheless, new ways of operating are needed for the future research use of these – despite all the caveats – useful big datasets.

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